

TERRA VISION

Integrated Earth Observation Based Platform, for Novel Services
to Enhance the Mining Life Cycle of Critical Raw Materials

D7.1 State of the Art in ARD

**T7.1: Development of synergistic framework of tools and
methods that will allow the production of Analysis Ready Data
and indices**

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ARD	Analysis Ready Data
CEOS	Committee on Earth Observation
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
DEM	Digital Elevation Model
DTM	Digital Terrain Model
EO	Earth Observation
ESA	European Space Agency
MODIS	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer
NBR	Normalized Burn Ratio
NDSI	Normalized Difference Snow Index
NDVI	Normalized Difference Vegetation Index
NDWI	Normalized Difference Water Index
ROI	Region Of Interest
SAR	Synthetic Aperture Radar
SoTA	State of The Art

H1 – EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable outlines a framework for generating Analysis Ready Data (ARD) from satellite observations, streamlining data preprocessing for Earth Observation (EO) applications. The modular and scalable framework consists of four levels—baseline data (L1), corrected data (L2), advanced data aggregation (L3), and multisensory data fusion (L4)—designed to enhance data quality, usability, and interoperability. This deliverable is a state of the art of the technologies required to build the framework.

Key processes include atmospheric correction, spatial alignment, radiometric calibration, data fusion, and AI-driven analysis, enabling applications such as land-use classification, change detection, and environmental monitoring. The framework leverages best practices and state-of-the-art, while integrating data from diverse sources such as satellites and drones.

H2 – GOAL/OBJECTIVES

The primary goal of this deliverable is to establish a robust and standardized framework based on state of the art of the technologies, for generating ARD from satellite and airborne

observations. By addressing the inherent complexities and inconsistencies in EO data, the framework aims to streamline the data preprocessing pipeline, enabling seamless integration of multi-source data and enhancing the quality, usability, and analytical value of satellite-derived datasets. The ultimate objective is to reduce preprocessing burdens for end users, promote interoperability across diverse datasets, and empower users to utilize high-quality ARD for a wide array of applications, including advanced analytics, machine learning, and environmental monitoring.

To achieve this goal, the deliverable focuses on several key objectives:

1. **Standardization:** Develop a consistent and modular processing pipeline to produce ARD ensuring minimal user effort and maximum usability.
2. **Advanced Data Processing:** Incorporate state-of-the-art techniques to enhance data quality and analytical readiness.
3. **Scalability and Modularity:** Design the framework with scalable processing levels to accommodate diverse user needs, ranging from basic corrections to advanced data fusion and machine learning applications.
4. **Interoperability:** Enable seamless integration of data across temporal and spatial scales, ensuring compatibility between different sensors, platforms, and applications.
5. **Accessibility:** Provide open-source tools and methodologies to democratize access to ARD generation, reducing the reliance on extensive computational resources and proprietary solutions.

H3 – METHODOLOGY

The methodology employed in this deliverable revolves around a modular and scalable framework for generating ARD from mostly satellite, but also airborne and in-situ sensors observations. It integrates state-of-the-art techniques and algorithms across four progressive processing levels: baseline data preprocessing, surface-level corrections, advanced data aggregation, and multisensory data fusion. Each stage builds upon the previous, employing innovative methods such as atmospheric correction, orthorectification, radiometric calibration, and pan-sharpening to enhance data quality and usability.

The framework also incorporates advanced AI-driven techniques for object detection, change detection, and semantic interpretation, ensuring adaptability to diverse user requirements and applications. These advanced methodologies not only improve accuracy and efficiency but also enable seamless integration into complex analytical workflows. By harnessing AI's transformative capabilities, the framework ensures that the resulting ARD products are optimized for interoperability, analytical readiness, and advanced machine learning applications, providing new levels of automation and insight.

H4 – OUTCOMES/CONCLUSIONS

The proposed framework for generating ARD offers a comprehensive, modular, and scalable solution to transform observations into high-quality, analysis-ready formats tailored for advanced analytics and machine learning applications. By integrating best practices and state-of-the-art methodologies across four progressive processing levels the framework enhances

data usability, interoperability, and analytical potential. Key outcomes include reduced preprocessing burdens, seamless multi-source data integration, and the creation of standardized, user-focused data products. This framework not only simplifies the use of EO data but also paves the way for more effective applications in environmental monitoring,

Key outcomes/conclusions in bullet points

- **Modular and scalable framework** for generating ARD from raw satellite observations, supporting diverse user needs and applications.
- **Enhanced usability and interoperability** of EO data through standardized preprocessing across four distinct levels.
- **Reduction in preprocessing burdens** by automating key steps.
- **Seamless integration of multi-source data**, including SAR, multispectral, and hyperspectral datasets, enabling advanced analytical and machine learning applications.
- **Creation of high-quality, analysis-ready data products** tailored to various domains, including environmental monitoring, disaster management, and resource management.
- **Improved accessibility** for researchers, data scientists, and EO professionals by leveraging open-source tools and advanced methodologies.
- **Facilitation of advanced analytical capabilities**, such as object detection, change detection, and semantic interpretation, to maximize the value of EO data for decision-making.

disaster management, and other domains reliant on EO insights.

1. Introduction

1.1 Deliverable Description

This deliverable describes a comprehensive framework for generating Analysis Ready Data (ARD) from satellite and plane observations, designed to streamline and standardize the data preprocessing pipeline for Earth Observation (EO) applications. The proposed framework consists of four distinct processing levels, where each level progressively transforms the data to enhance its quality and analytical potential, with key processes such as atmospheric correction, spatial alignment, radiometric calibration, data fusion, and advanced AI-driven analysis. The use of EO data for advanced analytics and machine learning is often hindered by challenges such as inconsistent data formats, sensor-specific distortions, and the need for extensive preprocessing. These issues complicate data integration, increase computational demands, and limit accessibility for non-expert users. This framework aims to reduce preprocessing burdens, facilitate seamless integration of multi-source data, and ensure high

interoperability for a wide range of user applications, from basic data processing to advanced machine learning and environmental monitoring.

1.2 Intended Audience

The framework is designed to streamline data usable for advanced analytics and machine learning applications while providing EO professionals with the tools needed to generate high-quality, interoperable data products tailored to diverse applications. These professionals can be:

- Researchers
- Data scientists
- Service providers
- Environmental monitoring entities

1.3 Deliverable structure and relation with other work packages/deliverables

This document is structured into two main sections, each focusing on a specific aspect of the topic. It begins with a **State of The Art** section, which introduces the concept of Analysis Ready Data (ARD) and highlights its importance in simplifying the use of Earth Observation (EO) data. This section provides a definition of ARD from the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS) and reviews several recent papers that discuss frameworks and methods for producing ARD, and ARD enhancement approaches.

Next, the **Proposed Framework** section describes a new ARD processing framework designed to transform observation data into analysis-ready formats. This framework is modular and scalable, with four progressive data processing levels: baseline data (Level 1), corrected data (Level 2), advanced data aggregation (Level 3), and multisensory data fusion (Level 4). Each level introduces additional preprocessing steps, corrections, or enhancements to improve the usability and analytical value of the data.

Finally, the document concludes with a summary of ARD's importance and the benefits of the proposed framework in making satellite data easier to use for advanced analytics and machine learning and next steps in the project..

2. State of the Art

The concept of ARD is essential for enhancing the usability of EO datasets by minimizing preprocessing burdens. Despite its utility, ARD lacks a universally accepted definition, which complicates efforts to standardize methods and achieve consistent outcomes.

2.1 Definition

The Committee of Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS) provides a specific definition for ARD. According to CEOS, ARD is defined as "satellite data" that has been processed with a minimum set of requirements. Furthermore, they are organized into a form that allows immediate analysis with minimum user effort. Interoperability through time and with other datasets is a key aspect of ARD. The ARD-related reviewed papers provide insights into various frameworks and approaches aimed at overcoming these challenges.

In addition to this definition, CEOS establishes detailed specifications for specific ARD products derived from satellite sensors. These include surface reflectance products for optical sensors, covering Multispectral and Hyperspectral sensors such as Sentinel-2, EnMAP, PRISMA, WorldView, and Pleiades. Notably, Sentinel-2 Level-2A (L2A) and EnMAP data products have already been approved as CEOS-ARD, ensuring standardized and reliable datasets for various applications.

Given the availability of these standardized ARD products from data providers and platforms like OpenEO, it is crucial to assess the added value of our approach. Our task aims to complement existing ARD frameworks by addressing specific challenges that persist despite these standardized products. This includes improving data harmonization, refining preprocessing pipelines for better interoperability, and exploring novel methodologies that enhance usability across diverse applications. By building upon the existing CEOS-ARD specifications, this work contributes to the ongoing effort to make EO data more accessible and analysis-ready.

2.2 Reviewed papers

2.2.1 S1-S2 ARD Framework

The Feb. 2022 paper "***A Flexible -Temporal and Multi-Modal Framework for Sentinel-1 and Sentinel-2 ARD***" (Upadhyay et al., 2022) proposes a ***Multi*** framework that emphasizes harmonizing Sentinel-1 SAR and Sentinel-2 multispectral data, offering a robust solution for producing ARD across temporal and spatial scales. It is designed for the automatic generation of on-demand, temporally matched Sentinel ARD for a user-defined Region of Interest (ROI).

Figure 1 framework that emphasizes harmonizing Sentinel-1 SAR and Sentinel-2 multispectral data,

Among their contributions are radiometric calibration, speckle filtering using Lee and Frost methods, and terrain correction incorporating Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) for Sentinel-1 data processing. For Sentinel-2, methods such as Sen2Cor are mentioned for atmospheric correction to produce Bottom-of-Atmosphere (BoA) reflectance data, as well as resampling methods. The open-source framework is implemented in Python and uses ESA’s SNAP toolbox, empowering users to generate ARD without requiring extensive computational resources.

Figure 2 Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) for Sentinel-1

Figure 3 Sentinel-2 Processing

2.2.2 STAR (Standardized ARD)

The Nov. 2023 paper “*Standardized Analysis Ready (STAR) data cube for high-resolution Flood mapping using Sentinel-1 data*” (S. Ghosh et al., 2023) proposes a framework focused on disaster management by automating Sentinel-1 preprocessing in the Google Earth Engine (GEE) environment. A comprehensive SAR preprocessing workflow is provided, which standardizes Sentinel-1 Ground Range Detected (GRD) data by applying corrections for radiometric noise, border artifacts, terrain slope, and local incidence angle.

Figure 4 ARD Framework defined in 2023 paper “Standardized Analysis Ready (STAR) data cube for high-resolution Flood mapping using Sentinel-1 data”

The STAR framework does also delve into noise reduction techniques such as border noise removal and speckle filtering methods. For radiometric terrain correction, it addresses distortions due to varying topographies using a DEM-based adjustment process. Smoothing and noise reduction are performed using a kernel-based smoothing to enhance image quality for flood delineation, and processes addressing disconnected pixels, projections and temporal composition are applied to complete the ARD process.

2.2.3 Sen2Chain

The Apr. 2024 paper “*Sen2Chain: An Open-Source Toolbox for Processing Sentinel-2 Satellite Images and Producing Time-Series of Spectral Indices*” (Revillion et al., 2024) presents Sen2Chain, a tool that automates the processing of Sentinel-2 data for generating time-series of spectral indices, aiming to simplify S2 data access and processing and addressing the increasing need for high-resolution EO data in fields like agriculture, disaster management, and ecology. The study examines some existing tools for accessing and processing S2 data, addressing tools such as MAJA and Sen2Cor for L2A level data, and Sen2r and Sen2-Agri to handle large amounts of EO data.

Sen2Chain is a software tool to download, manage and process large volumes of L2 data covering broad spatial and temporal extents. It automates downloading S2 images from multiple providers via the EODAG API and applies atmospheric corrections using ESA’s Sen2Cor to generate Level-2A reflectance data. It also provides four customizable cloud masks based on Sen2Cor outputs and spectral bands, and can calculate up to 11 indices like NDVI, NDWI or NBR. For time-series extraction, Sen2Chain offers tools for extracting statistical summaries for regions or specific points, enabling temporal analysis.

Figure 5 Main stages in downloading, processing and storing Sentinel-2 images and their products with the Sen2Chain methodology.

2.2.4 ARD enhancement

The Mar. 2024 paper *“On the analysis-readiness of spatio-temporal Earth data and suggestions for its enhancement”* (Baumann, 2024) delves into the foundational challenges faced in defining and achieving ARD. It proposes a datacube-based approach for enhanced usability and automation. This is achieved by critiquing the current ARD practices, highlighting the generator-centric nature of most EO data and the lack of interoperability and standardization, it proposes using spatio-temporal raster data structured as datacubes to improve accessibility and integration. It also examines data fusion, that is, combining datasets from different sources (e.g., optical and radar) without manual intervention. Finally it focuses on harmonizing coordinate reference systems, resolutions, and temporal alignment for seamless integration.

2.3 Existing ARD Tools

OpenEO is an open-source platform that simplifies the generation of ARD by providing a standardized interface for accessing and processing EO data across multiple cloud backends. It abstracts complex preprocessing tasks, allowing users to perform basic atmospheric corrections, spatial alignment, and data fusion without requiring in-depth knowledge of individual satellite data processing methods. Thus, making it easier for users to achieve ARD at the most basic levels of processing. The openEO Python client offers a user-friendly API for processing data, with detailed documentation available on various use cases, including optical and radar data preprocessing. For more details, refer to: [openEO ARD Use Cases](#), [openEO Python Client Cookbook](#), [Copernicus Dataspace openEO Radar ARD](#).

It is also important to highlight that OpenEO has already been deployed within the Terravision architecture to facilitate satellite data acquisition. This existing integration provides a robust foundation for expanding its capabilities within the project. Given its standardised approach to EO data processing, OpenEO presents a compelling option for the deployment of new algorithms, enabling seamless integration with existing workflows and infrastructure. Furthermore, its scalability and compatibility with multiple cloud backends make it a strong candidate not only for enhancing data processing efficiency but also for serving as the core framework upon which the project's broader data processing architecture can be built and extended.

3. Proposed framework

The proposed ARD framework is designed to convert data into formats optimized for advanced analytical and machine learning applications. Building on a thorough review of the SoTA techniques based on ARD-producing tools¹, the framework has been tailored to incorporate best practices and innovative methodologies. This framework enables seamless processing of data into analysis-ready formats by applying various transformations, corrections, and enhancements. The proposed framework is intended to be modular and scalable, accommodating a range of user needs from minimally processed data to fully aggregated, multisensory data products.

3.1 Data Processing Levels

¹ Some examples are AROSICS, Snappy-esa, GDAL, FORCE, IR-MAD, Py6S, Scikit-learn, Rasterio or PySTAC.

The following ARD framework introduces a four-level data processing scheme that reflects a progressive approach to transforming data, so the different service providers can select the level at which they wish the data to be processed.

3.1.1 Level 1: Baseline Data

Level 1 (L1) is the most basic processing level and serves as the foundation for subsequent preprocessing stages. It undergoes minimal preprocessing and retains much of its raw characteristics, including potential artifacts like noise, geometric distortions and atmospheric disturbances like haze, fog or clouds.

L1 Data includes mostly satellite imagery, but also airborne data collected from flight missions or drones and in-situ sensor-based measurements from various sources. These datasets typically undergo initial processing steps such as georeferencing and radiometric calibration to ensure spatial and spectral accuracy. However, they may still contain distortions, inconsistencies, or noise that require further corrections—such as atmospheric adjustments, geometric refinements, or enhanced calibration—to be fully prepared for advanced analysis and integration into downstream applications.

3.1.2 Level 2: Corrected Data

Level 2 (L2) advances this with surface-level corrections, such as atmospheric adjustments, spatial alignment, and orthorectification which are essential for preparing data for specific applications. The progressive nature of these levels ensures flexibility, allowing users to select the processing stage that best suits their analytical requirements.

- **Atmospheric corrections:** mitigation of atmospheric interference to restore accurate reflectance values in satellite imagery, ensuring that the observed data reflects true surface characteristics without the distortion introduced by atmospheric conditions.
SoTA methods:
 - **Sen2Cor:** atmospheric correction processor for the Sentinel-2 mission under the Copernicus programme. It processes Sentinel-2 Level-1C Top-Of-Atmosphere (TOA) data to generate Level-2A Bottom-Of-Atmosphere (BOA) reflectance products, correcting for atmospheric effects. Additional outputs include Aerosol Optical Thickness (AOT), Water Vapour (WV) maps, and Scene Classification (SCL) maps with quality indicators for cloud and snow probabilities. (Louis et al., 2019)
 - **SMAC:** Simplified Method for Atmospheric Corrections of satellite measurements. It is a semi-empirical approximation of the radiative transfer in the atmosphere. (Rahman & Dedieu, 1994)
 - **6S:** Second Simulation of a Satellite Signal in the Solar Spectrum, advanced radiative transfer code used for atmospheric correction by simulating solar radiation reflection in various atmospheric and surface conditions. (Kotchenova et al., 2006)

- **FLAASH:** Fast Line-of-sight Atmospheric Analysis of Spectral Hypercubes, based on the MODTRAN4 radiative transfer model to estimate atmospheric effects. (Anderson et al., 2002)
- > Open-source implementations: SMAC (Python package)², SCP plugin for QGIS, Sen2Cor (SNAP)³
- **Orthorectification:** geometrical correction to remove distortions caused by the sensor's perspective and terrain variations.
 - **Physical models:** dense DTMs and advanced non-parametric models, addressing challenges like elevation discontinuities and geometric distortions for accurate medium-scale mapping. (Boccardo et al., s. f.)
 - **Rational Function Model:** sensor-independent method for image exploitation by modeling the relationship between image and object space using ratios of polynomials. (Vincent Tao et al., s. f.)
 - **Ortho-WTLS:** enhances the accuracy and robustness of RFM-based orthorectification by using a weighted total least squares estimator. (Ge et al., 2017)
 - > Open-source implementations: Orthority⁴ (Python API), Orbview⁵ (Python), Orfeo ToolBox...
- **Spatial alignment:** alignment of satellite images so that their pixels correspond to the same geographic location.
 - **Feature-based alignment:** U-Net-based segmentation to transform multimodal alignment into monomodal alignment, deep feature extraction with CNNs, and a multi-level architecture. (Wu et al., 2023)
 - **ILNA-SPDE:** a Bayesian hierarchical model that addresses spatial misalignment in spatio-temporal data from in situ and satellite sources. (He & Wong, 2024)
 - > Open-source implementations: SatAlign⁶ (Python package), SNAP, QGIS with Georeferencer plugin...
- **Radiometric calibration:** includes atmospheric correction to account for aerosol and scattering effects (SMAC, Simplified Method for Atmospheric Correction), topographic correction to address illumination differences due to terrain (C-correction or Minnaert correction, based on Digital Elevation Models), and adjacency effect correction to minimize distortions caused by light scattering from nearby areas. Additionally, a Bidirectional Reflectance Distribution Function (BRDF) correction is

² <https://github.com/olivierhagolle/SMAC>

³ <https://step.esa.int/main/snap-supported-plugins/sen2cor/sen2cor-v2-12/>

⁴ <https://github.com/leftfield-geospatial/orthority>

⁵ <https://github.com/mpfaffenberger/orthorectification>

⁶ <https://github.com/IPL-UV/satalign>

applied to normalize reflectance values as if observed from a nadir perspective (Frantz, 2019).

- **Pansharpening:** used to enhance the spatial resolution of multispectral images by fusing them with high-resolution panchromatic images. Multispectral images provide detailed spectral information across multiple wavelengths but often have lower spatial resolution, while panchromatic images capture a broader range of wavelengths in grayscale at a higher resolution. By combining these datasets, pansharpening produces images with both high spatial detail and rich spectral information.
 - **CNNs:** residual convolutional neural network architecture that focuses on high-frequency detail extraction and reconstruction. The approach leverages both spatial and spectral fidelity indicators to achieve a balance between detail enhancement and spectral preservation. (Ciotola et al., 2021)
 - **Laplacian Pyramid Pansharpening Network (LPPN):** multi-scale structures and the modulation transfer function (MTF) to separate and fuse images. The network combines recursive layers for parameter efficiency and across-scale loss functions to enhance spatial and spectral fidelity. (Jin et al., 2022)
 - **SSconv:** Full-resolution training framework for deep learning-based pansharpening. It avoids resolution shifts and loss of information by training models directly on high-resolution data, introducing spectral and spatial loss components to ensure fidelity and leveraging a target-adaptive fine-tuning mechanism for better generalization. (Y. Wang et al., 2021)
- **Cloud and shadow detection and masking:** applying methods to identify and mask clouds and their shadows, ensuring subsequent analyses focus on cloud-free pixels.
 - **Fmask:** Spectral-Feature-Based method which calculates cloud probabilities dynamically, effectively detects thick and thin clouds. (Zhu & Woodcock, 2012)
 - **MFC:** Spectral-Spatial-Feature-Based methods which incorporate spatial features like edges and textures to handle complex surfaces, often used with high-resolution images. (Li et al., 2017)
 - **Tmask:** Spectral-Temporal-Feature-Based method that compares predicted clear-sky images with cloud-covered ones for precise detection. (Zhu & Woodcock, 2014)
 - **MCD-RPCA:** Spectral-Spatial-Temporal-Feature-Based method that integrates principal component analysis with temporal change detection. (H. Zhang et al., 2021)
 - **UDTCDA:** Multi-Source-Feature-Based method which uses a MODIS cloud-free reflectance database for universal cloud detection. (Sun et al., 2016)
 - **MSCFF:** Machine-Learning-Based algorithm that employs CNNs to extract multi-scale features for cloud and shadow detection. (Li et al., 2019)
 - **Inpainting:** reconstruction of cloud-obscured regions using data from multi-temporal, multi-source inputs or advanced techniques like deep learning to restore missing visual information. (Czerkawski et al., 2022)

- **GANs:** uses a generator and a discriminator in a competitive process to create realistic outputs by learning to model the underlying data distribution. (B. Ghosh et al., 2021)
 - **SeqDMs:** uses diffusion processes to reconstruct cloud-free remote sensing images by integrating multi-modal (e.g., SAR) and multi-temporal information. (Zhao & Jia, 2023)
 - **DiffCR:** diffusion framework for high-performance cloud removal from optical satellite images, incorporating conditional encoders, time embedding, and a denoising autoencoder. (Zou et al., 2023)
 - **Dsen2-CR:** deep residual neural network architecture with SAR-optical data fusion and a cloud-adaptive loss function to remove clouds from Sentinel-2 imagery. (Meraner et al., 2020)
 - **UnCRtainTS:** attention-based architecture and multivariate uncertainty quantification to achieve state-of-the-art cloud removal from multi-temporal optical satellite imagery. (Ebel et al., 2023)
- > Open-source implementations: s2cloudmask⁷ (Python package), SRCdip⁸ (Python package), MDSA, CVAE, AMGAN, SPAGAN and Memory Net models⁹ (Python), SNAP Cloud Masking for Fmask...
- **Topographic correction:** mitigating effects caused by terrain slope and orientation on observed reflectance, enabling more equitable comparisons between pixels.
 - **C Correction:** non-Lambertian method that adjusts reflectance values by incorporating the relationship between terrain reflectance and local illumination angle, commonly applied to Top of Atmosphere (ToA) reflectance because it avoids the need for atmospheric correction. (Richter et al., 2009)
 - **Gamma Correction:** Considers both the solar illumination and sensor viewing geometry. (Richter et al., 2009)
 - **Modified Minnaert (MM):** It performs well in diverse rugged terrains, showing superior results for reducing topographic effects across multiple regions and sensors. (Richter et al., 2009)

> Open-source implementations: GRASS plugin for QGIS (i.topo.corr), SNAP (C correction and MM), Topocor¹⁰ for MM method (Python)...
 - **Temporal and multi-sensor normalization:** adjusting data from different acquisition dates and sensors to create a consistently comparable database. This includes processing steps to harmonize spectral, spatial, and temporal resolutions.
 - **Kernel Manifold Alignment (KEMA):** nonlinear manifold learning method for aligning datasets of different dimensions that aligns features from multi-

⁷ <https://github.com/daleroberts/s2cloudmask>

⁸ <https://github.com/strath-ai/satellite-cloud-removal-dip>

⁹ <https://github.com/littlebeen/Cloud-removal-model-collection>

¹⁰ <https://github.com/luiscartor/topocor>

sensor and multi-temporal images to a common latent space by solving a generalized eigenvalue problem. (Tuia et al., 2016)

- **Multirule-based RRN:** combines strategies like pseudo-invariant features (PIF) identification using spectral and spatial-invariant pixels, regression modelling and integration of spectral and spatial rules to enhance the normalization process for multi-sensor satellite images. (Xu et al., 2023)

Most of these tasks apply to both airborne and spaceborne data, but some are more specific to one type. Cloud masking and pan-sharpening are used in airborne data as flights can avoid clouds and capture cloud-free, high-resolution imagery that will be used as ground truth for the mentioned models. However, geometric corrections are more common for spaceborne data due to distortions from Earth's curvature, sensor geometry, and terrain effects.

3.1.3 Level 3: Advanced Data Aggregation

Level 3 (L3) shifts the focus to aggregated and derived products within individual datasets. Processes at this stage include data fusion from similar sources, such as integrating multiple SAR images for improved analysis. Derived indices like NDVI, NDWI, and NDSI are also computed at this level.

Additionally, multimodal artificial intelligence techniques are also applied at this level to further extend the framework's analytical capabilities: Semantic Captioning involves generating descriptive and human-readable text which provides insights by interpreting satellite imagery, Object Detection identifies and locates specific features within the dataset, and Change Detection compares data across different timeframes to quantify changes in the environment or landscape, vital for monitoring.

- **Land Cover/Land Use Classification:** classify and monitor characteristics such as vegetation, water, soil, artificial structures and agriculture, urban development, or conservation features over time.
 - **EarthMapper:** Machine learning-based approach for Land Cover classification and analysis, emphasizing flexibility and ease of use. It integrates pre-trained models and workflows for processing and analyzing geospatial data, making it accessible for various applications like environmental monitoring and urban planning. Provides researchers and practitioners with a straightforward and effective tool for land classification tasks. (Kemker et al., 2018)
 - **SrSeg:** Deep learning-centric approach, specializing in semantic segmentation to achieve fine-grained identification and mapping of Land Cover types from high-resolution remote sensing imagery. By focusing on segmentation models, it provides precise pixel-level classification, which is particularly useful for applications requiring detailed spatial resolution, such as urban infrastructure mapping or ecosystem analysis. (Xie et al., 2022)
- **Change Detection:** comparing multi-temporal satellite imagery to monitor changes in mining activities, such as pit expansion, tailings dam growth, or vegetation loss, using spectral differences, machine learning, or deep learning techniques.
 - **GETNET:** deep learning framework for hyperspectral image change detection that uses a mixed-affinity matrix and a 2D CNN to improve feature extraction

- and generalization, with a new dataset for comparing methods and superior performance in real hyperspectral data. (Q. Wang et al., 2019)
- **CDFormer**: transformer encoder-based framework for hyperspectral image change detection that incorporates space and time encodings to guide the model in exploiting spatial and temporal change information, using a self-attention component to capture correlations between bi-temporal features. (Ding et al., 2022)
 - **ADHR-CDNet**: change detection network for multispectral image change detection that introduces a high-resolution Differential Pyramid Module (DPM) to extract multiscale and multilevel changed features, effectively distinguishing substantive changes from pseudochanges. (X. Zhang et al., 2022)
 - **Mask-CDNet**: deep learning-based change detection framework with two collaborative modules: one for roughly predicting change areas and matching unaligned images, and another for refining these predictions to improve accuracy and robustness against noise. (Bu et al., 2020)
 - **COCRF**: class-prior object-oriented conditional random field framework for change detection that integrates binary and multiclass tasks, using class-prior knowledge to improve unary potentials and reduce spectral variability, with effective interaction between binary and multiclass results, object constraints to enhance local smoothness and an adaptive parameter estimation strategy. (Shi et al., 2022)
- **Object Detection**: identify and locate specific objects within a region of interest, providing both their class labels and spatial coordinates, known as bounding boxes. It is useful for applications such as land use classification, monitoring environmental changes, detecting natural disasters, and tracking objects like vehicles, ships, or infrastructure. By automating the extraction of relevant information from large-scale geospatial data it enhances decision-making processes in mining sites.
 - **MMDetection**: a comprehensive open-source toolbox for object detection and instance segmentation based on PyTorch. It offers modular components, supports various detection frameworks, and provides pre-trained models, facilitating research and development in object detection (Chen et al., 2019).
 - **GroundingDINO**: an open-set object detector that integrates Transformer-based DINO with grounded pre-training. This model can detect arbitrary objects specified by human inputs, such as category names or referring expressions, enhancing generalization to novel objects (S. Liu et al., 2024).
 - **Co-DETRs**: collaborative hybrid assignment training scheme. By incorporating multiple auxiliary heads with one-to-many label assignments, Co-DETR enhances the learning efficiency and effectiveness of DETR models without adding inference complexity (Zong et al., 2023)
 - **YOLO**: YOLO is a series of real-time object detectors. YOLOv7 achieves superior speed and accuracy by incorporating novel training strategies and architectural improvements, setting new benchmarks for real-time object detection performance (C.-Y. Wang et al., 2022). YOLOv9 further pushes the

boundaries of real-time detection by integrating more efficient feature extraction layers, improved attention mechanisms, and dynamic input scaling (C.-Y. Wang et al., 2024).

- **Semantic interpretation via Voice or Geospatial Chatbots:** vLLM-based chatbots are powered by vision-language models that combine natural language processing (NLP) with computer vision to enable multi-modal interactions. These chatbots can process and understand both textual and visual inputs, such as images or videos, allowing them to answer questions, generate captions, and provide contextually relevant responses based on visual cues.
 - **LlaVa 1.5 (Large Language and Vision Assistant):** a multi-modal conversational AI model that integrates vision and language capabilities, enabling it to process images alongside text for tasks like visual question answering and detailed image-based discussions. It combines pre-trained vision encoders and large language models to deliver context-aware, image-grounded conversational outputs and provides seamless in-domain training for different contexts, like remote sensing (H. Liu et al., 2024).
 - **Qwen2-VL:** an advanced vision-language model that introduces a Naive Dynamic Resolution mechanism, enabling dynamic processing of images with varying resolutions into different numbers of visual tokens. This approach enhances the model's ability to generate efficient and accurate visual representations, closely aligning with human perceptual processes (P. Wang et al., 2024).

3.1.4 Level 4: Multisensory Data Fusion

Level 4 represents the outermost level of the ARD framework, where data from various sources, such as SAR, multispectral, and hyperspectral data from satellites, drones, and in-situ sensors, are seamlessly combined. This multisensory fusion maximizes the information content and enhances analysis potential.

3.2 High-Level Workflow

To ensure clarity and coherence, the ARD framework follows a systematic approach that accounts for the acquisition, transformation, and validation of data from multiple sources. This high-level workflow ensures a streamlined and adaptable approach to ARD processing while maintaining rigorous quality control measures across different sensor types and data applications. The workflow is structured as follows:

3.2.1 Data Ingestion & Acquisition

This first stage involves the collection of data from multiple sources, including satellite platforms, airborne sensors like drone imagery and aerial photography, and in-situ measurements. This step also includes the standardization of metadata and format conversions to ensure interoperability across different sensor types.

3.2.2 Preliminary Data Structuring

This phase organizes data based on acquisition parameters, such as spatial resolution, temporal coverage, and spectral bands. During this stage, data are categorized into distinct processing tracks, ensuring that satellite, airborne, and drone-based inputs receive tailored treatment. Initial quality control checks are conducted to assess data integrity, coverage completeness, and sensor-specific artifacts, ensuring a solid foundation for subsequent processing steps.

3.2.3 Level 2 Processing

This stage involves the application of geometric corrections, including orthorectification and spatial alignment, to ensure consistency across different acquisitions; atmospheric corrections such as cloud masking are performed to mitigate distortions caused by atmospheric influences.

3.2.4 Level 3 Processing

Multi-temporal and multi-modal datasets are integrated to generate derived products such as spectral indices, including NDVI and NDSI, and change detection outputs. AI-driven methods for object detection, land use classification, and semantic interpretation are applied to enhance the analytical value of processed data. Validation against reference datasets ensures consistency and accuracy in classification outputs.

3.2.5 Level 4 Processing

Focuses on combining heterogeneous data sources, such as optical, SAR, LiDAR, and ground-truth measurements, to create enhanced spatial and spectral representations.

3.2.6 Final Data Packaging

Processed data are structured into standardized output formats compatible with downstream applications such as GIS platforms and machine learning pipelines. Metadata is ensures traceability of processing steps and reproducibility of results. Data are exported at various ARD levels, allowing users to select the appropriate processing depth based on their analytical requirements.

Figure 6 Workflow of the proposed ARD framework.

3.3 Applied ARD

The following section contains examples on the different open-source ARD methods tested from external and Terravision Data.

3.3.1 Methods

To evaluate the effectiveness of some of the approaches discussed, we have conducted extensive testing of these methods using some placeholder datasets, provided by the original authors. By applying the selected open-source Python tools, the results highlight the benefits of integrating these methods into our workflow. The following sections detail the tested ARD methods and key findings.

3.3.1.1 Orthorectification: Orbview

Different algorithms and utilities assist the orthorectification process. The code is optimized for performance using Numba's Just-In-Time (JIT) compilation and offers an easy-to-follow pipeline that uses Python libraries such as GDAL, rasterio or sardem.

Figure 7 Comparison of satellite images: on the left, the original image with geometric distortions; on the right, the orthorectified image with terrain and perspective corrections (satellite image acquired by OrbView-3).

3.3.1.2 Pan-Sharpener: MUCNN

MUCNN employs a convolutional neural network (CNN) architecture to perform pan-sharpening, aiming to produce high-quality, high-resolution multispectral images. This method enhances pansharpening by leveraging a spectral-spatial convolution (SSconv) and a multiscale injection branch, which are then combined with a standard convolution. The model has been trained and tested using PyTorch.

Figure 8 Comparison on a single spectral channel: the top-left image corresponds to a high-resolution panchromatic image, the top-right is the original low-resolution multispectral channel, and the bottom image shows the pansharpened result. Images obtained from <https://github.com/liangjiandeng/PanCollection>.

3.3.1.3 Cloud and shadow masking: SCR-dip

Satellite-Cloud-Removal-dip utilizes Deep Image Prior (DIP) for cloud removal in satellite imagery. DIP is used to inpaint missing or cloud-covered regions of images without requiring additional training data. The implementation in Python leverages PyTorch Lightning, allowing users to provide target images and corresponding masks.

Figure 9 Comparison of satellite images with and without masked clouds and shadows (Sentinel-2 image captured over a region in Scotland).

3.3.2 Data

This section samples the flight data collected by DIMAP from the Canteras mining site, located in southern Spain, from TERRAVISION project.

Figure 10 Three of 160 extracted hyperspectral bands, corresponding to (roughly) the blue, green and red channels respectively.

Combined bands

Real location

Lat 37°06'40" N, Long 3° 42' 12" W

Figure 11 Comparison of the combination of extracted BGR bands (left) and the real location (right).

Figure 12 Surface DEM (Digital Elevation Model).

4. Conclusion and Next Steps

Analysis Ready Data refers to data processed to ensure interoperability and immediate usability with minimal user effort, as defined by CEOS. The proposed ARD framework builds on this concept, offering a modular and scalable approach that applies advanced corrections, aggregations, and multisensory fusion. It addresses the stated challenges by standardizing preprocessing steps, ensuring interoperability, and enhancing data usability for seamless and optimized analytics and ML applications.

By facilitating harmonized integration across different EO sensors and platforms, the framework enhances interoperability, allowing users to work with multi-source data without additional preprocessing burdens. Additionally, its modular structure ensures adaptability to diverse analytical needs, from environmental monitoring to resource management. Ultimately, this framework enables researchers and decision-makers to leverage high-quality ARD more efficiently, reducing technical barriers and accelerating data-driven insights.

It is important to note that this deliverable primarily serves as a state-of-the-art analysis and an initial conceptualization of the ARD framework. A detailed workflow, including step-by-step processing methodologies, will be presented in the upcoming deliverable (D7.2 – M18). Over the coming months, as part of Task 7.1, the framework will be designed and its initial implementation carried out, drawing upon the various technologies analysed in this deliverable. Particular consideration will be given to the architectural design of Terravisión and the services developed within the project. Notably, this deliverable highlights the potential use of OpenEO as potential ARD toolbox, and its use will be evaluated on each stage of the proposed framework, leveraging the existing deployed infrastructure already in use within the project.

Additionally, it is important to emphasise that throughout the next few months, the software design of the ARD system will need to integrate the different technologies outlined in this document, as well as those identified in other tasks within WP7. At the same time, a highly significant process is currently underway to coordinate activities within Work Packages 7 and 8, as well as across multiple Work Packages, including WP6/7 and WP9/10.

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